

Appendix 1: List of my publications involving Iranian spiders, as of February 9th, 2023.

1. Szűts, T., Szabó, K., **Zamani, A.**, Forman, M., Miller, J., Oger, P., Fabregat, M., Kovács, G. & Gál, J. (2023). A study in scarlet: integrative taxonomy of the spider genus *Loureedia* (Araneae: Eresidae). *Diversity* **15**: 238.
2. **Zamani, A.**, Marusik, Y. M. & Szűts, T. (2023). A survey of the spider genus *Dysdera* Latreille, 1804 (Araneae, Dysderidae) in Iran, with fourteen new species and notes on two fossil genera. *ZooKeys* **1146**: 43–86.
3. **Zamani, A.**, Vahtera, V., Sääksjärvi, I. E. & Carvalho, L. S. (2023). The effect of sampling bias on evaluating the diversity and distribution patterns of Iranian spiders (Arachnida: Araneae). *Diversity* **15**: 22.
4. Nadolny, A. A., Marusik, Y. M., Kronestedt, T., Kovblyuk, M. M. & **Zamani, A.** (2022). New cases of teratological deformities in wolf spiders (Araneae: Lycosidae). *Arachnology* **19(2)**: 585–590.
5. **Zamani, A.**, Nadolny, A. A. & Dolejš, P. (2022). New data on the spider fauna of Iran (Arachnida: Araneae), Part X. *Arachnology* **19(2)**: 551–573.
6. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2022). New taxonomic data on Zodariinae (Araneae: Zodariidae) of Azerbaijan, Iran, Afghanistan and Pakistan. *Zootaxa* **5155(3)**: 423–438.
7. **Zamani, A.**, Nadolny, A. A., Esysunin, S. L. & Marusik, Y. M. (2022). New data on the spider fauna of Iran (Arachnida: Araneae), Part IX. *Arachnology* **19(Special Issue)**: 358–384.
8. **Zamani, A.**, Stockmann, M., Magalhaes, I. L. F. & Rheims, C. A. (2022). New taxonomic considerations in the spitting spider family Scytodidae (Arachnida: Araneae). *Zootaxa* **5092(2)**: 151–175.
9. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2021). Three new species of spiders (Aranei) from Iran. *Caucasian Entomological Bulletin* **17(2)**: 451–458.
10. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2021). Two new species of Liocranidae (Arachnida: Aranei) from the Caucasus and northern Iran. *Arthropoda Selecta* **30(4)**: 557–564.
11. **Zamani, A.**, Nadolny, A. A., Esysunin, S. L. & Marusik, Y. M. (2021). New data on the spider fauna of Iran (Arachnida: Araneae), part VIII. *Zoosystematica Rossica* **30(2)**: 279–297, suppl. 298–306.
12. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2021). A new genus and ten new species of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) from Iran. *ZooKeys* **1054**: 95–126.
13. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2021). Two new species of Theridiidae from Iran, and the revalidation of *Enoplognatha submargarita* Yaginuma & Zhu, 1992 (Arachnida: Araneae). *Arachnology* **18(8)**: 957–964.

14. **Zamani, A.**, Chatzaki, M., Esyunin, S. L. & Marusik, Y. M. (2021). One new genus and nineteen new species of ground spiders (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) from Iran, with other taxonomic considerations. *European Journal of Taxonomy* **751**: 68–114.
15. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2021). Revision of the spider family Zodariidae (Arachnida, Araneae) in Iran and Turkmenistan, with seventeen new species. *ZooKeys* **1035**: 145–193.
16. **Zamani, A.**, Mirshamsi, O. & Marusik, Y. M. (2021). ‘Burning Violin’: the medically important spider genus *Loxosceles* (Araneae: Sicariidae) in Iran, Turkmenistan, and Afghanistan, with two new species. *Journal of Medical Entomology* **58(2)**: 666–675.
17. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2021). New taxa of six families of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) from Iran. *Zoology in the Middle East* **67(1)**: 81–91.
18. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2020). New species of Filistatidae, Palpimanidae and Scytodidae (Arachnida: Araneae) from southern Iran. *Acta Arachnologica* **69(2)**: 121–126.
19. **Zamani, A.** & Bosselaers, J. (2020). The spider family Oecobiidae (Arachnida: Araneae) in Iran, Afghanistan and Turkmenistan. *European Journal of Taxonomy* **726**: 38–58.
20. **Zamani, A.**, Dimitrov, D., Weiss, I., Alimohammadi, S., Rafiei-Jahed, R., Esyunin, S. L., Moradmand, M., Chatzaki, M. & Marusik, Y. M. (2020). New data on the spider fauna of Iran (Arachnida: Araneae), Part VII. *Arachnology* **18(6)**: 569–591.
21. Esyunin, S. L. & **Zamani, A.** (2020). ‘Conundrum of esoterica’: on the long-forgotten genus *Eutittha* Thorell, 1878, with new taxonomic considerations in *Cheiracanthium* C. L. Koch, 1839 (Araneae: Cheiracanthiidae). *Journal of Natural History* **54(19–20)**: 1293–1323.
22. Nadolny, A. A. & **Zamani, A.** (2020). A new species of wolf spiders of the genus *Lycosa* (Aranei: Lycosidae) from Iran. *Zoosystematica Rossica* **29(2)**: 205–212.
23. **Zamani, A.**, Altın, Ç. & Szűts, T. (2020). A black sheep in *Eresus* (Araneae: Eresidae): taxonomic notes on the ladybird spiders of Iran and Turkey, with a new species. *Zootaxa* **4851(3)**: 559–572.
24. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2020). A new and easternmost species of *Loureedia* (Aranei: Eresidae) from Iran. *Arthropoda Selecta* **29(2)**: 239–243.
25. Azarkina, G. A. & **Zamani, A.** (2020). The first description of the female of *Heliophanus xerxesi* Logunov, 2009 (Araneae: Salticidae) from Iran. *Revue suisse de Zoologie* **127(1)**: 21–25.
26. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2020). A survey of Phrurolithidae (Arachnida: Araneae) in southern Caucasus, Iran and Central Asia. *Zootaxa* **4758(2)**: 311–329.

27. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2020). A review of Agelenini (Araneae: Agelenidae: Ageleninae) of Iran and Tajikistan, with descriptions of four new genera. *Arachnology* **18(4)**: 368–386.
28. **Zamani, A.**, Hosseini, M. S. & Moradmand, M. (2020). New data on jumping spiders of Iran, with a new species of *Salticus* (Araneae: Salticidae). *Arachnologische Mitteilungen* **59**: 63–66.
29. Montemor, V. M., West, R. C., **Zamani, A.**, Moradmand, M., Wirth, V. von, Wendt, I., Huber, S. & Guadanucci, J. P. L. (2020). Taxonomy of the genus *Ischnocolus* in the Middle East, with description of a new species from Oman and Iran (Araneae: Theraphosidae). *Zoology in the Middle East* **66(1)**: 76–90.
30. **Zamani, A.**, Marusik, Y. M. & Šestáková, A. (2020). On *Araniella* and *Neoscona* (Araneae, Araneidae) of the Caucasus, Middle East and Central Asia. *ZooKeys* **906**: 13–40.
31. Esyunin, S. L. & **Zamani, A.** (2019). Taxonomic remarks on two *Drassodes* species (Araneae, Gnaphosidae) from Iran. *Acta Arachnologica* **68(2)**: 63–71.
32. Cokendolpher, J. C., **Zamani, A.** & Snegovaya, N. Y. (2019). Overview of Arachnids and Arachnology in Iran. *Journal of Insect Biodiversity and Systematics* **5(4)**: 301–367.
33. Hosseinpour, A., **Zamani, A.**, Azizi, K., Moemenbellah-Fard, M. D. & Soltani, A. (2019). Survey of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in southwestern Iran, with new records. *Ecologica Montenegrina* **22**: 204–213.
34. Moradmand, M., **Zamani, A.** & Jäger, P. (2019). An Afrotropic element at the north-western periphery of the Oriental Region: *Pseudomicrommata mokranica* sp. nov. (Araneae: Sparassidae). *Revue suisse de Zoologie* **126(2)**: 249–256.
35. **Zamani, A.**, Tanasevitch, A. V., Nadolny, A. A., Esyunin, S. L. & Marusik, Y. M. (2019). New data on the spider fauna of Iran (Arachnida: Aranei). Part VI. *Euroasian Entomological Journal* **18(4)**: 233–243.
36. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2019). The spider genera *Azerithonica* and *Tegenaria* (Aranei: Agelenidae: Tegenariini) in Iran. *Arthropoda Selecta* **28(2)**: 291–303.
37. Azarkina, G. & **Zamani, A.** (2019). The Aelurillina Simon, 1901 (Aranei: Salticidae) of Iran: a check-list and three new species of *Aelurillus* Simon, 1884 and *Proszynskiana* Logunov, 1996. *Arthropoda Selecta* **28(1)**: 83–97.
38. **Zamani, A.**, Marusik, Y. M., Soofi, M., Koponen, S., Caleb, J. T. D. & Šestáková, A. (2019). First record of *Poltys nagpurensis* (Araneae: Araneidae) from Iran. *Arachnologische Mitteilungen* **57**: 4–7.
39. **Zamani, A.** & Crews, S. C. (2019). The flattie spider family Selenopidae (Araneae) in the Middle East. *Zoology in the Middle East* **65(1)**: 79–87.

40. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2018). The first report on the spider fauna (Arachnida: Araneae) of the Lut Desert, Iran. *Acta Arachnologica* **67(2)**: 67–75.
41. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2018). A new species of hersiliid spiders (Aranei: Hersiliidae) from Iran. *Euroasian Entomological Journal* **17(4)**: 273–275.
42. Schwendinger, P. & **Zamani, A.** (2018). A new species of *Phyxioschema* (Araneae: Dipluridae) from Iran. *Revue suisse de Zoologie* **125(2)**: 283–289.
43. **Zamani, A.**, Seiedy, M., Saboori, A. & Marusik, Y. M. (2018). The spider genus *Pterotracha* in Iran, with the description of a new genus (Araneae, Gnaphosidae). *ZooKeys* **777**: 17–41.
44. **Zamani, A.**, Mirshamsi, O., Kashani, G. M. & Karami, L. (2018). New data on the spider fauna of Iran (Arachnida: Araneae), Part V. *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics* **13(2, for 2017)**: 183–197.
45. **Zamani, A.**, Marusik, Y. M. & Malek-Hosseini, M. J. (2018). A new species of *Tegenaria* Latreille, 1804 (Araneae: Agelenidae) from western Iran. *Zootaxa* **4444(1)**: 95–97.
46. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2018). New species and records of Filistatidae (Arachnida: Aranei) from Iran. *Arthropoda Selecta* **27(2)**: 121–128.
47. **Zamani, A.**, Mirshamsi, O., Marusik, Y. M., Hatami, M. & Maddahi, H. (2017). The spider genus *Oecobius* in Iran, with description of two new species (Araneae: Oecobiidae). *Oriental Insects* **51(4)**: 330–337.
48. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2017). Six new species of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) from Iran. *Oriental Insects* **51(4)**: 313–329.
49. **Zamani, A.**, Mirshamsi, O., Dolejš, P., Marusik, Y. M., Esyunin, S. L., Hula, V. & Ponel, P. (2017). New data on the spider fauna of Iran (Arachnida: Araneae), Part IV. *Acta Arachnologica* **66(2)**: 55–71.
50. Tahami, M. S., **Zamani, A.**, Sadeghi, S. & Ribera, C. (2017). A new species of *Loxosceles* Heineken & Lowe, 1832 (Araneae: Sicariidae) from Iranian caves. *Zootaxa* **4318(2)**: 377–387.
51. **Zamani, A.** & André, J.-M. (2017). First record of the orb-weaver spider *Araneus grossus* (C. L. Koch, 1844) in Iran (Araneae: Araneidae). *Newsletter of the British Arachnological Society* **139**: 6.
52. **Zamani, A.**, Mirshamsi, O. & Marusik, Y. M. (2017). Description of a new species of *Hersiliola* and the male of *Duninia rheimsae* Marusik & Fet, 2009 from Iran (Araneae: Hersiliidae). *Turkish Journal of Zoology* **41(4)**: 624–629.
53. **Zamani, A.** & Mozaffarian, F. (2017). Further spider (Arachnida: Araneae) material deposited in the Agricultural Zoology Museum of Iran (AZMI), Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection. *Arachnologische Mitteilungen* **54**: 8–20.

54. Nadolny, A. A. & **Zamani, A.** (2017). A new species of burrowing wolf spiders (Araneae: Lycosidae: *Lycosa*) from Iran. *Zootaxa* **4286(4)**: 597–600.
55. **Zamani, A.**, Hosseinpour, A., Azizi, K. & Soltani, A. (2017). A new species of the jumping spider genus *Evarcha* (s. lat.) from southwestern Iran (Araneae: Salticidae). *Peckhamia* **150.1**: 1–5.
56. Esyunin, S. L., **Zamani, A.** & Tuneva, T. K. (2017). On two poorly known Eurasian dictynid species (Aranei: Dictynidae), with a description of a new genus. *Arthropoda Selecta* **26(1)**: 49–62.
57. **Zamani, A.**, Marusik, Y. M. & Koponen, S. (2017). First description of the male of the easternmost *Harpactea* species, *H. parthica* (Araneae: Dysderidae). *Zootaxa* **4238(2)**: 258–262.
58. Kiany, N., Sadeghi, S., Kiany, M., **Zamani, A.** & Ostovani, S. (2017). Additions to the crab spider fauna of Iran (Araneae: Thomisidae). *Arachnologische Mitteilungen* **53**: 1–8.
59. Malek-Hosseini, M. J. & **Zamani, A.** (2017). A checklist of subterranean arthropods of Iran. *Subterranean Biology* **21**: 19–46.
60. **Zamani, A.** (2016). A new species of *Spariolenus* from South Iran (Aranei: Sparassidae). *Arthropoda Selecta* **25(4)**: 421–422.
61. **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2016). A new species and new distribution records of *Zaitunia* from Iran (Araneae: Filistatidae). *Zoology in the Middle East* **62(4)**: 373–376.
62. Marusik, Y. M. & **Zamani, A.** (2016). A new species of *Sahastata* (Aranei, Filistatidae) from Southern Iran. *Vestnik Zoologii* **50(3)**: 267–270.
63. **Zamani, A.** (2016). Predation on *Cyrtopodion scabrum* (Squamata: Gekkonidae) by *Steatoda paykulliana* (Araneae: Theridiidae). *Arachnida - Rivista Aracnologica Italiana* **8**: 12–15.
64. Moradi, M., Yağmur, E. A., Moradi Ghrakhloo, P. & **Zamani, A.** (2016). First record of *Filistata lehtineni* Marusik & Zonstein, 2014 for the fauna of Iran (Araneae: Filistatidae). *Biharean Biologist* **10(1)**: 53–54.
65. Sadeghi, H., Ahmadi, M., **Zamani, A.** & Jabaleh, I. (2016). A study on the spider fauna of Dargaz and Kalat Counties in Razavi Khorasan Province, Iran (Arachnida: Araneae). *Biharean Biologist* **10(1)**: 4–7.
66. Moradmand, M., **Zamani, A.** & Jäger, P. (2016). On the genus *Cebrennus* Simon, 1880 in Iran with description of a new species from Iranian Central Desert (Araneae: Sparassidae). *Zootaxa* **4121(2)**: 187–193.
67. **Zamani, A.**, Marusik, Y. M. & Berry, J. W. (2016). A new species of *Paratheuma* (Araneae: Dictynidae) from Southwestern Asia and transfer of the genus. *Zoology in the Middle East* **62(2)**: 177–183.

68. Mirshamsi, O., **Zamani, A.** & Marusik, Y. M. (2016). A survey of Hersiliidae (Arachnida: Araneae) of Iran with description of one new genus and two new species. *Journal of Natural History* **50(23–24)**: 1447–1461.
69. **Zamani, A.**, Mirshamsi, O., Rashidi, P., Marusik, Y. M., Moradmand, M. & Bolzern, A. (2016). New data on the spider fauna of Iran (Arachnida: Aranei), part III. *Arthropoda Selecta* **25(1)**: 99–114.
70. Namaghi, H. S., Safari, A., Entezari, E. & **Zamani, A.** (2016). New faunistic records of spiders (Araneae) from Razavi Khorasan Province, Iran. *Zoology and Ecology* **26**: 18–21.
71. Malek Hosseini, M. J., **Zamani, A.** & Sadeghi, S. (2015). A survey of cave-dwelling spider fauna of Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad and Fars Provinces, Iran (Arachnida: Araneae). *Revista Ibérica de Aracnología* **27**: 90–94.
72. Marusik, Y. M. & **Zamani, A.** (2015). First description of the male of *Tegenaria zamanii* Marusik & Omelko, 2014 (Araneae: Agelenidae) from northern Iran. *Zootaxa* **4052(2)**: 226–228.
73. Marusik, Y. M. & **Zamani, A.** (2015). Additional new species of Filistatidae (Aranei) from Iran. *Arthropoda Selecta* **24(4)**: 429–435.
74. **Zamani, A.**, Mirshamsi, O., Jannesar, B., Marusik, Y. M. & Esyunin, S. L. (2015). New data on spider fauna of Iran (Arachnida: Araneae), Part II. *Zoology and Ecology* **25(4)**: 339–346.
75. Mirshamsi, O., Marusik, Y. M., **Zamani, A.**, Kashefi, R. & Moradmand, M. (2015). Fauna Iranica: I. Annotated checklist of the spiders of Iran (Arachnida: Araneae). *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics Supplement 1*: 1–108.
76. Marusik, Y. M. & **Zamani, A.** (2015). The spider family Filistatidae (Araneae) in Iran. *ZooKeys* **516**: 123–135.
77. **Zamani, A.** (2015). The spider collection (Arachnida: Araneae) of the Zoological Museum of the Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection, with new species records for Iran. *Arachnologische Mitteilungen* **50**: 11–18.
78. Shahi, M., Shahi, A., Khademi, Z., **Zamani, A.**, Nakhaii, A. & Rafinejad, J. (2015). Loxoscelism: a case report from Bandar Abbas in south of Iran. *Hormozgan Medical Journal* **18(5)**: 467–473.
79. **Zamani, A.** (2014). First report of a mermithid nematode (Enoplea: Mermithida) parasitizing the crab spider *Heriaeus spinipalpus* (Araneae: Thomisidae). *Acta Arachnologica* **63(2)**: 63–64.
80. Marusik, Y. M., **Zamani, A.** & Mirshamsi, O. (2014). Three new species of mygalomorph and filistatid spiders from Iran (Araneae, Cyrtaucheniidae, Nemesiidae and Filistatidae). *ZooKeys* **463**: 1–10.

81. Namaghi, H. S., Kaykhosravi, M. & **Zamani, A.** (2014). New data and records of spiders from North-Eastern Iran (Arachnida: Araneae). *Serket* **14(2)**: 105–110.
82. **Zamani, A.**, Nikmagham, Z., Allahdadi, M., Ghassemzadeh, F. & Mirshamsi, O. (2014). New data on the spider fauna of Iran (Arachnida: Araneae). *Zoology in the Middle East* **60(4)**: 362–367.
83. **Zamani, A.**, Mirshamsi, O., Savoji, A. & Shahi, M. (2014). Contribution to the distribution of spiders with significant medical importance (Araneae: *Loxosceles* and *Latrodectus*) in Iran, with a new record for the country. *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics* **10(1)**: 57–66.
84. **Zamani, A.** (2014). The spitting spider genus *Scytodes* (Araneae: Scytodidae) in Iran. *Arachnologische Mitteilungen* **47**: 41–44.
85. **Zamani, A.** (2014). The first record of family Segestriidae Simon, 1893 (Araneae: Dysderoidea) from Iran. *Serket* **14(1)**: 15–18.
86. **Zamani, A.** & Rafinejad, J. (2014). First record of the Mediterranean Recluse Spider *Loxosceles rufescens* (Araneae: Sicariidae) from Iran. *Journal of Arthropod-Borne Diseases* **8(2)**: 228–231.
87. Mirshamsi, O., Hatami, M. & **Zamani, A.** (2013). New record of the Mediterranean recluse spider *Loxosceles rufescens* (Dufour, 1820) and its bite from Khorasan Province, northeast of Iran (Aranei: Sicariidae). *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics* **9(1)**: 83–86.